

on wheat. Incubation, larval, and pupal periods lasted 5, 94-96, and 33-35 d, respectively. Total development period from egg to adult emergence was 132-136 d. Pupation was 30%.

We surveyed rice-growing areas in Sep 1989 to locate other alternate hosts. LF was found on nine host plants of Gramineae family and the order Graminales: *Agropyron repens* (L.)

Beauv., *Brachiaria mutica* (Forsk.) Stapf., *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv., *Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) Scop., *D. setigera* Roth ex R&S, *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link., *E. crus-galli* L., *Saccharum munjo* L., and *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers.

All hosts except *B. mutica*, *E. colona*, and *E. crus-galli* were not known before. Larvae were found

feeding on these hosts in and alongside the ricefields. The perennial weed *A. repens* was most preferred (85% damaged leaves), followed by *E. crus-galli*, *S. halepense*, and *E. colona*. Least preferred hosts were *D. setigera*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *B. mutica*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, and *Saccharum munjo* (3.7-20.3%). ■

Predation of yellow stem borer (YSB) moths by wolf spider

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The wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* Boes. et Strand common in ricefields feeds on a variety of prey, including hoppers, collembolans, flies, and the mirid predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*. Studies have shown that the spider exhibits a functional response: consump-

Functional response of the wolf spider to yellow stem borer moths. a' = attack rate, Th = handling time.

tion of prey by individual spiders increases with prey density.

We studied the functional responses of the wolf spider to 1-d-old female YSB moths. Spiders were reared in the laboratory and starved for 3 d prior to the experiment. A spider was released in 19-cm-diam mylar cages containing 1, 2, 3, 5, or 10 moths, with five replications. Three stages of rice TN1 were used as substrates: 13- and 35-d-old plants and rice stubble.

L. pseudoannulata searched for YSB moths most efficiently on 13-d-old rice plants (see figure). At this stage, there was less foliage and the search area was smaller than on 35-d-old rice plants with more than 10 tillers and denser leaves. It is also possible that moths hide better in 35-d-old plants.

Moth consumption was lowest on rice stubble, perhaps because the color of moths and stubble looked similar to the spider. ■

Electroantennogram technique for studying olfactory sensitivity of insects to volatile compounds

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Volatile compounds produced by plants or conspecific species may have complex effects on an insect's fitness in a given environment. Host plant-derived volatile compounds may be used by insects to colonize the plant. Compounds produced by conspecifics may be used to locate mates.

Identifying the volatile compounds mediating the interaction between an

insect and its environment may have potential in insect management strategies. However, volatile compounds produced by a plant or an insect are numerous (a rice plant may produce as many as 30 to 40 volatile compounds) and often chemically very closely related.

Identifying compounds that are biologically active requires screening a large number of compounds rapidly. Electroantennogram suits this purpose. The technique is based on the principle that biologically active volatile chemicals pass through microtubules on the antenna of the insect and bind with receptor proteins, initiating electrical reactions in the dendrites of the olfactory cells as receptor membrane depolarization.

The electroantennogram measures the sum of many olfactory receptor potentials, recorded more or less simultaneously by an electrode connected to the sensory epithelium of an insect.

The procedure involves connecting the tip and the base of an insect's antenna to a recording and a reference electrode, respectively. The electrodes are connected to an amplifier and an oscilloscope (Fig. 1). The electrodes are silver nitrate-coated silver wires placed inside glass capillaries containing a saline solution (0.1% KCl). Charcoal-filtered air generated by a pump is blown continuously over the antenna through a delivery tube.

The olfactory stimulus (pure chemicals applied on filter paper or leaves) placed in a disposable pasteur pipette is inserted into the side of the delivery tube. A calibrated amount of air is passed through the pasteur pipette for a specific period of time (usually 1 s). The air carries the odorant chemicals over the antenna. The electrical signals generated